

Virtual Biopsy by Using Artificial Intelligence–based Multimodal Modeling of Binational Mammography Data

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Background: Computational models based on artificial intelligence (AI) are increasingly used to diagnose malignant breast lesions. However, assessment from radiologic images of the specific pathologic lesion subtypes, as detailed in the results of biopsy procedures, remains a challenge.

Purpose: To develop an AI-based model to identify breast lesion subtypes with mammograms and linked electronic health records labeled with histopathologic information.

Materials and Methods: In this retrospective study, 26 569 images were collected in 9234 women who underwent digital mammography to pretrain the algorithms. The training data included individuals who had at least 1 year of clinical and imaging history followed by biopsy-based histopathologic diagnosis from March 2013 to November 2018. A model that combined convolutional neural networks with supervised learning algorithms was independently trained to make breast lesion predictions with data from 2120 women in Israel and 1642 women in the United States. Results were reported using the area under the receiver operating characteristic curve (AUC) with the 95% DeLong approach to estimate CIs. Significance was tested with bootstrapping.

Results: The Israeli model was validated in 456 women and tested in 441 women (mean age, 51 years \pm 11 [SD]). The U.S. model was validated in 350 women and tested in 344 women (mean age, 60 years \pm 12). For predicting malignancy in the test sets (consisting of 220 Israeli patient examinations and 126 U.S. patient examinations with ductal carcinoma in situ or invasive cancer), the algorithms obtained an AUC of 0.88 (95% CI: 0.85, 0.91) and 0.80 (95% CI: 0.74, 0.85) for Israeli and U.S. patients, respectively ($P = .006$). These results may not hold for other cohorts of patients, and generalizability across populations should be further investigated.

Conclusion: The results offer supporting evidence that artificial intelligence applied to clinical and mammographic images can identify breast lesion subtypes when the data are sufficiently large, which may help assess diagnostic workflow and reduce biopsy sampling errors.

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Breast cancer was the most commonly diagnosed cancer in 2020, with an estimated 2.3 million cases (1). Because of this high incidence, improving mammography accuracy by classifying breast lesions into malignant or benign has been a topic of interest in the medical image–computing field. Although pathologic analysis remains the reference standard for breast lesion diagnosis, its invasive procedure can be a source of potential discomfort and anxiety. Reducing the unnecessary biopsy rate can therefore considerably decrease health care costs and avoid unnecessary patient distress.

Because of the extensive use of digital mammography (DM) in diagnosis of breast cancer, we sought to assess whether a model combining deep learning and supervised learning could be applied to DM to noninvasively characterize breast lesions. This would have the potential to facilitate treatment planning and minimize unnecessary biopsies. Considering the variety of structural features of

various lesions, we investigated whether the DM images are likely to vary according to the distinctive morphologic structures that reflect the differences in cell organization and arrangement. Although histopathologic and immunohistochemistry tests are performed at a much higher spatial resolution than DM, radiologic features could potentially provide a characterization of a range of cellular and subcellular components observed in several breast lesion types.

The purpose of our study differs from previous work (2–8) with artificial intelligence (AI) models trained on retrospective screening mammography data for the detection of breast cancer. Those studies developed deep neural networks to assist radiologists reading mammograms, resulting in AI-based models with impressive performances at the range of the radiologists. Notably, their patient population is composed mostly of women with normal and cancer-free mammography. However, our cohort is based on a screening population with examinations that led to biopsies. We

Abbreviations

AI = artificial intelligence, AUC = area under the receiver operating characteristic curve, DM = digital mammography

Summary

An artificial intelligence–based algorithm trained with mammograms and linked electronic health records classified biopsied breast lesions and may improve personalized care management.

Key Results

- In a retrospective study, a model trained with mammograms from 2120 Israeli women predicted breast lesion malignancy with an area under the receiver operating characteristic curve (AUC) of 0.88.
- At 99% sensitivity, the model could prevent 13% of unnecessary biopsies while missing 1.3% of malignancies.
- The one-versus-rest algorithm achieved an AUC of 0.85 for the invasive lesions class, but generalizability should be further investigated.

selected only screening mammograms with annotated lesions (visible findings) that were later part of a diagnostic workup following abnormal screening results. This selection criteria help us explore the value of the AI technology to guide lesion management and complement the work of radiologists. In addition to the cancer or noncancer classification, this study aimed to assess whether biopsied lesions detected at DM could be further classified into finer subtypes: ductal carcinoma in situ; invasive, high-risk lesions; benign lesions; and others (Table E1 [online]). Additionally, we investigated whether including patients' clinical characteristics could improve the accuracy of the algorithms. Therefore, we benchmarked the performance of the models built on only imaging-based features, clinical data, and a combination of both.

Materials and Methods

This retrospective study was approved by the respective institutional research ethics review boards and written informed consent was waived. A total of 11 655 of 14 587 women in our cohort were previously included in a breast lesion classification model, which was solely based on imaging data without clinical records (9). Ethnic categories in the electronic health records were self-reported by study participants. The code used for training, developing, and testing the AI models is publicly available (https://github.com/IBM/fuse-med-ml/tree/virtual_biopsy_ensemble_methods/fuse_examples/classification/virtual_biopsy_ensemble_methods).

Study Design

Our study was composed of two independent cohorts from Israel and the United States. The Israeli and U.S. data set included, respectively, records of 3017 and 2336 women. These women underwent DM examinations in a single breast imaging center (Israeli cohort; between April 2013 and December 2016) and 19 breast imaging centers (U.S. cohort; between March 2013 and November 2018). In both cohorts, women were included in the study if their records included at least 1 year of medical history followed by biopsy-based diagnosis summarized in pathologist reports (Fig 1). For each woman who was eligible, we selected the

last mammographic examination before the biopsy occurrence and looked 1 year back to include additional examinations if they had DM-annotated lesions linked to the pathologic results of the biopsy. We also included additional mammographic data from the United Kingdom and other U.S. breast imaging centers solely for the purpose of pretraining our algorithms, which has shown to result in performance improvements (9) (Fig 2).

Each examination contained one to 10 DM images and linked detailed electronic health records of the patients before mammography (Appendix E1 [online]). The data were split at the patient level (70% training, 15% validation, and 15% test) (Table 1).

Breast Lesion Classes

The pathologic analyses in the breast were acquired from histopathologic reports from core-needle biopsy and, when applicable, were confirmed or changed on the basis of surgical biopsy. The results are grouped into three categories according to standard management in clinical practice: malignant, benign, and high-risk lesions (eg, lobular carcinomas in situ, atypia, or atypical hyperplasia). Similar to previous studies (10,11), we categorized malignant lesions into ductal carcinoma in situ and invasive. We then combined a remainder of the data set, composed of radial scars and papillary lesions, into the group labeled *others*.

This division criteria resulted in five categories: ductal carcinoma in situ, invasive, others, benign, and high-risk lesions (Fig 3). A list of pathologic analyses mapped to their classes is in Appendix E2 (online) and Table E1 (online).

Model Architecture

For each mammographic examination, the input data consisted of DM images and the detailed clinical history of the women. First, we used XGBoost (12) (version 1.2.0; <https://xgboost.ai>) to investigate the prediction ability of the clinical data (Fig 4A). For each class, we trained a One versus Rest XGBoost classifier using the clinical characteristics. We identified a subset of clinical and radiographic features that showed the greatest contribution to the prediction for all classes (Figs E1, E3, E4 [online]), such as age, breast density, and symptoms. This subset of features was the final set used for prediction in the clinical models (Fig 4A). In parallel, a multiclass convolutional neural network was trained on DM images for the prediction of breast lesion categories (Fig 4B). The convolutional neural network architecture was a submodel of that suggested by Tlusty et al (9) containing only the full image branch (Fig E2, Appendix E3 [online]). The results were determined at the examination level to allow a comparison with the clinical setting. To go from the image to the examination-level predictions, we computed an average of the image predictions per viewpoint (craniocaudal and mediolateral oblique) and per left and right sides (Fig 4B). Finally, the resulting imaging features were concatenated with the clinical features subset and fused into other One versus Rest XGBoost models.

We benchmarked the models using clinically based features, image-based features, and a combination of both. This procedure was performed individually for the U.S. and Israeli cohorts. The six models were further evaluated in their respective independent

Figure 1: Selection criteria of patients and digital mammography (DM) examinations. **(A, B)** Inclusion and exclusion criteria in the Israeli cohort **(A)** and U.S. cohort **(B)**. Starting from a screening population, we excluded all patients with breast cancer history or breast implants (step 1). The mammographic examination had to include annotated lesions for which the radiologist recommended a biopsy. Therefore, any patient without biopsy procedures in their records was excluded (step 2), or those with biopsy results without a pathologic description were excluded (step 3). Examinations without DM or examinations that led to pathologic reports that were different from the defined five breast lesion classes were also excluded (steps 4 and 5). Individuals without a minimal clinical history of 1 year were not considered (step 6). **(C)** Outcomes of the index mammography study were derived from a subsequent biopsy result, which was performed within a maximum period of 12 months after the study. For all women in the cohort, the latest mammograms before biopsy were selected. A few women had images with annotated findings from previous examinations that happened up to a year before the index date (ie, annotations were linked to pathologic results of the biopsy). Clinical characteristics such as body mass index (BMI) and use of fertility hormones were collected before index date. Images from previous DM studies were considered if they contained annotated lesions. Max = maximum, Min = minimum.

test sets. Finally, we investigated the generalization of the models by training and testing in different cohorts.

Statistical Analysis

We used the Fisher exact test for categorical features and the Student *t* test for continuous features to estimate the univariable association of variable distributions in cancer outcome. A two-sided *P* value less than .05 was considered to indicate statistical significance. We corrected for multiple hypotheses by using the Bonferroni correction. We report our results on the test sets using the area under the receiver operating characteristic curve (AUC) with the 95% DeLong CI (13). For these statistical analyses, we used Scikit-Learn (version 1.0.1; scikit-learn.org).

To evaluate the statistical significance of clinical data and compare performance on different test sets, we used bootstrapping and DeLong tests, respectively (Appendix E4 [online]). Both tests were performed with the pROC (14) package in R (version 4.1.2; R Project for Statistical Computing).

Results

Study Patients

Application of the inclusion and exclusion criteria resulted in 3017 women in the Israeli cohort and 2336 women in the U.S. cohort (Fig 1). The Israeli training set consisted of mammography in 2120 women (mean age, 51 years \pm 12 [SD]; mean body mass index, 26.1 kg/m² \pm 5.5) (Table 1). The test set consisted of examinations of 441 women (mean age, 51 years \pm 11; mean body mass index, 26.0 kg/m² \pm 5.5). In the U.S. cohort, 1685 examinations in 1642 women (mean age, 61 years \pm 11; mean body mass index, 31.0 kg/m² \pm 7.1) were used for training. The data used for the test cohort consisted of 353 examinations from 344 women (mean age, 60 years \pm 12; mean body mass index, 31.8 kg/m² \pm 7.6).

In the Israeli and U.S. data sets, there was a total of 16 651 and 2392 lesions with diagnosis confirmed by biopsy from 8245 and 4964 images, respectively. Detailed statistics of mammography

Figure 2: Schematic illustration of different training and testing scenarios. Top: Pretraining of the deep learning models was performed by using data from the United Kingdom and a large data set from the United States to classify images into malignant, benign, and normal data sets. We further used those model weights to initialize the model on the task of breast lesion classification. Middle: Model development (training and tuning) is performed by using either imaging data only, clinical data only, or both. Bottom: Models were individually trained on Israeli and U.S. development data sets and were tested in their own geography. Generalizability across continents was investigated by testing the U.S. model on the Israeli test set, and the Israeli model on the U.S. test set. DCIS = ductal carcinoma in situ, LCC = left craniocaudal, LMLO = left mediolateral oblique, RCC = right craniocaudal, RMLO = right mediolateral oblique.

belonging to each lesion class in training, validation, and test sets are shown in Table 1.

We aggregated each woman’s clinical data with her image information. For each DM examination, 1832 clinical features were available, including risk factors for breast cancer (15). To better understand the disparities between clinical features in cancerous and noncancerous lesions, we performed a univariable analysis between examinations that had a biopsy that was positive and negative for cancer (Tables 2, 3). In the Israeli data set, the distributions of all risk factors differed significantly (Table 2; $P < .05$, Bonferroni adjusted). The use of hormonal replacement therapy was more frequent in women diagnosed with cancers, in accordance with what is commonly found in the literature (15). In the U.S. data set, cancer and noncancer classes (Table 3) had significant differences only in age (mean, 63 years vs 59 years for malignant and benign groups;

$P < .001$) and presence of a lump detected by a physician (20.2% vs 10%, respectively; $P < .001$).

AI Performance Evaluation

Test sets.—We evaluated the trained models on the test sets from the U.S. cohort and the Israeli cohort (Tables 4, E2 [online]). Expectedly, classes with small test set sizes (ie, others and high-risk lesions) resulted in inaccurate predictions with large CIs.

Overall, our AI model exhibited the potential to correctly assess breast lesion type classification in the remaining groups. In the test set from the United States, integrating imaging and clinical information in the model achieved an AUC of 0.74 (95% CI: 0.65, 0.83) for ductal carcinoma in situ, 0.83 (95% CI: 0.77, 0.88) for invasive carcinomas, and 0.72 (95% CI: 0.66, 0.77) for benign lesions. In the Israeli

Table 1: Characteristics of Israeli and U.S. Women in Training, Validation, and Test Sets

Characteristic	Training Set	Validation Set	Test Set
Israel data set			
No. of women	2120	456	441
No. of examinations	2120	456	441
No. of images	5797	1208	1240
Age (y)	51 ± 12	52 ± 12	51 ± 11
Most recent BMI (kg/m ²)	26.1 ± 5.4	26.1 ± 5.4	26.0 ± 5.5
Age at first menstruation (y)	12.5 ± 1	12.5 ± 0.9	12.6 ± 1.4
Postmenopause	685/2120 (32.3)	172/456 (38)	146/441 (33.1)
Examination ground-truth label			
Benign	1725/2120 (81.4)	380/456 (83.3)	346/441 (83)
High risk	133/2120 (6.3)	33/456 (7.2)	29/441 (7)
DCIS	375/2120 (18)	101/456 (22.1)	78/441 (18)
Invasive	686/2120 (32.4)	144/456 (32)	142/441 (32.2)
Others	33/2120 (2)	13/456 (3)	7/441 (2)
U.S. data set			
No. of women	1642	350	344
No. of examinations	1685	357	353
No. of images	3506	722	736
Age (y)	61 ± 11	60 ± 12	60 ± 12
Most recent BMI (kg/m ²)	31.0 ± 7.1	30.9 ± 8.5	31.8 ± 7.6
Age at first menstruation (y)	12.7 ± 1.7	12.7 ± 1.8	12.5 ± 1.7
Postmenopause	917/1685 (54.4)	207/357 (58)	196/353 (56)
Examination ground-truth label			
Benign	956/1685 (57)	202/357 (57)	205/353 (58.1)
High risk	60/1685 (4)	11/357 (3.1)	10/353 (3)
DCIS	173/1685 (10.3)	44/357 (12.3)	40/353 (11.3)
Invasive	440/1685 (26.1)	89/357 (25)	86/353 (24.4)
Others	100/1685 (6)	23/357 (6.4)	17/353 (5)

Note.—Mean data are ± SDs. Postmenopause data and ground-truth data are numbers of mammographic examinations and data in parentheses are percentages. Because one single mammography image can contain multiple lesions of different types, examinations are labeled with more than one class; therefore, percentages do not sum up to 100. The data from both cohorts were split into training, validation, and test sets in a stratified manner to preserve the frequency of breast lesion classes. BMI = body mass index, DCIS = ductal carcinoma in situ.

test set, performance was even higher, likely because of the larger sample size used for training the models (AUCs: 0.76 [95% CI: 0.72, 0.83; $P = .07$], 0.85 [95% CI: 0.82, 0.89; $P = .07$], and 0.82 [95% CI: 0.77, 0.87; $P = .02$], respectively). However, in none of these breast lesion groups did the patients' clinical characteristics contribute significantly to the final prediction.

In the Israeli cohort, the model achieved an AUC of 0.88 (95% CI: 0.85, 0.91) for predicting cancer. Images alone achieved an AUC of 0.87 (95% CI: 0.83, 0.90), and clinical data alone achieved an AUC of 0.79 (95% CI: 0.75, 0.84). When clinical features were concatenated to the image-based features before training the AI model, the AUC did not improve ($P = .17$, bootstrap analysis). We found no evidence of a difference in cancer prediction for the U.S. cohort ($P = .16$). Finally, when evaluating the models' generalizability to external data sets (training in Israeli data and testing in the U.S. data, and testing in Israeli data and training in U.S. data), we observed lower performance than these results. The performance of the models trained on Israeli data dropped when tested on U.S. data ($P <$

.001 for both benign lesions and for cancer vs noncancer prediction), which was expected based on differences between health policies and demographics of populations in these areas. Similarly, the models trained in the United States and tested in Israel resulted in lower performances ($P = .04$ for ductal carcinoma in situ, $P = .004$ for invasive carcinomas, and $P < .001$ for malignancy prediction).

We compared the malignancy diagnostic performance of our models to the performance reflected by the radiologists' assessment in both data sets (Fig 5A). AI system performance reached the level of the radiologists in the classification of lesions according to the mammography-based Breast Imaging Reporting and Data System. We set the models' prediction threshold to this operation point, corresponding to 98.2% sensitivity in the validation set (95% CI: 97.6, 98.9; Israel, 448 of 456; United States, 351 of 357). Based on of images and clinical data, the Israeli and U.S. models correctly interpreted 155 of 157 (98.7%) and 121 of 125 (96.8%) malignant mammographic examinations in their respective test sets. For predicting invasive carcinomas (Fig 5B), we used an operation point of 91% sensitivity in the

Figure 3: Examples of digital mammograms from the data set. The bottom images correspond to an enlarged annotated region drawn by the radiologist (blue contour was removed to better see the lesions). **(A)** Right craniocaudal screening mammogram in a 52-year-old woman shows ductal carcinoma in situ. Regional heterogeneous calcifications are seen in the central middle right breast (arrow, bottom image). Ductal carcinoma in situ was later confirmed at core biopsy. **(B)** Right mediolateral oblique image in a 70-year-old woman with heterogeneously dense breasts and obscure small masses shows invasive carcinoma. Large dystrophic calcifications in the upper outer aspect of the right breast, 10:00 region, were found to be Breast Imaging and Reporting Data System category 4 (arrow, bottom image). The patient was diagnosed with invasive ductal carcinoma confirmed at tissue biopsy. **(C)** Left mediolateral oblique view in a 52-year-old woman shows a high-risk, circumscribed, isodense 9-mm mass (arrow, bottom image) in the posterior-inferior left breast. Stereotactic guided core-needle biopsy was performed. Pathologic results confirmed lobular carcinoma in situ after biopsy. **(D)** An image from the “others” group. Left craniocaudal view in a 61-year-old woman with calcifications (arrow, bottom image). Stereotactic guided core biopsy of the left breast calcifications confirmed intraductal papilloma. **(E)** Benign lesion. Right mediolateral oblique view in a 68-year-old woman presenting for a 6-month follow-up because of a small focal nodular asymmetry (arrow, bottom image) found in the right breast. US-guided core biopsy for further histologic analysis was recommended; the patient was later diagnosed with apocrine metaplasia.

validation sets, corresponding to the diagnostic performance of fine-needle aspiration of ductal invasive and lobular invasive carcinomas according to Farras Roca et al (16). The Israeli and U.S. models were able to correctly diagnose 74.6% (106 of 142) and 63% (54 of 86) of invasive carcinomas, respectively.

We specified a range of acceptable sensitivities for potential clinical use and evaluated the number of false-positive findings our model would have prevented. At 99% sensitivity, the Israeli model would have prevented 13% of unnecessary biopsies and missed 1.3% of malignancies.

Race subgroups.—To investigate whether the results consistently generalize across ethnicities, we evaluated both models’ performance in subgroups of ethnicity in the U.S. test set, as the information was available (Fig 6). Participants’ self-reported ethnicity was extracted from electronic health records and consisted of the following categories: African American, Asian, Pacific Islander, White, and other. The U.S. model showed AUCs of 0.77 (95% CI: 0.70, 0.85) and 0.86 (95% CI: 0.79, 0.92) for women who were White and African American, respectively, whereas the Israeli model showed AUCs of 0.77 (95% CI: 0.70, 0.84) and 0.67 (95% CI: 0.57, 0.78), respectively. We found no evidence of differences in AUCs across ethnicities ($P = .30$ and $.35$, respectively, for the U.S. and Israeli models).

Discussion

We examined the feasibility of an artificial intelligence (AI) model to classify biopsied breast lesions. Whereas routine radiologic work focuses on the task of cancer versus benign classification, we explored a more challenging task of classifying lesions into their pathologic types using linked clinical data in addition to mammograms. The purpose was to assist in risk assessment, treatment planning, and reducing errors in pathologic findings from unsuccessful sampling of the tissue by the biopsy. Additionally, because approximately 75% of breast biopsies in the United States yield benign results (17), using an AI system to decrease false-positive findings can be of substantial value. In distinguishing cancer versus noncancer lesions, the model trained on the Israeli population predicted breast lesion malignancy with an area under the receiver operating characteristic curve (AUC) of 0.88 (95% CI: 0.85, 0.91) and a sensitivity of 90%, outperforming the recent study by Wu et al (18). At 99% sensitivity, the algorithm could prevent 13% of unnecessary biopsies while missing 1.3% of malignancies, similar to the results reported by Wu et al. Moreover, both U.S. and Israeli models generalized across White and African American subpopulations. In the pathologic classification, our best-performing algorithms achieved an AUC of 0.76 (95% CI: 0.72, 0.83), 0.85 (95% CI: 0.82, 0.89), and 0.82 (95% CI:

Figure 4: Outline of the model architecture to predict breast lesion subtypes. Input is a set of digital mammograms from an examination; usually both views of the breast (craniocaudal and mediolateral oblique, sometimes with additional supplementary views) and clinical data (1832 features). A1 shows selection of top clinical features for each lesion class prediction using XGBoost algorithm and Shapley additive explanations (SHAP) values. The final set of clinical features is defined as the union of the individual classes' top 20 most-contributing features. B1 shows the multiclass convolutional neural network (CNN), which is trained on each image for the class prediction. B2 shows the aggregated image-level predictions by taking an average of each view and side to have their representation per mammographic examination. The final models are trained on three sets of features: A2, top clinical data only; B3, imaging features only; and both. C_i = subset of most important clinical features for class i , LCC = left craniocaudal, LMLO = left mediolateral oblique, p_i = convolutional neural network predicted probability of an image to belong to class i , RCC = right craniocaudal, RMLO = right mediolateral oblique.

Table 2: Univariable Analysis of Relationship between Patient Demographics and Medical History to Breast Cancer Diagnosis in Israeli Data Set

Clinical Characteristic	No. of Mammography Examinations ($n = 3017$)	Examinations with Cancer Biopsy ($n = 1081$)	Examinations with Noncancer Biopsy ($n = 1936$)	Adjusted P Value
Age (y)	3017/3017 (100)	58 ± 13	48 ± 10	<.001
Most recent BMI (kg/m ²)	3017/3017 (100)	27.4 ± 5.6	25.3 ± 5.2	<.001
Age at first menstruation (y)	2003/3017 (66.4)	13 ± 1	12 ± 1	.01
Past benign breast diseases	311/3017 (10.3)	72/1081 (6.7)	239/1936 (12.3)	<.001
Months since first DM	1016/3017 (33.7)	14.7 ± 21.8	10.4 ± 17.7	<.001
Family history				
Has family member with breast cancer	854/3017 (28.3)	333/1081 (30.8)	521/1936 (26.9)	.002
First-degree family member with breast cancer	450/3017 (14.9)	191/1081 (17.7)	259/1936 (13.4)	<.001
Medications				
Past use of fertility hormones	815/3017 (27.0)	337/1081 (31.2)	478/1936 (24.7)	<.001
Past use combined hormones	407/3017 (13.5)	189/1081 (17.5)	218/1936 (11.3)	<.001
Symptoms				
Current symptom (eg, palpable lump, nipple discharge or retraction)	342/3017 (11.3)	96/1081 (8.9)	246/1936 (12.7)	<.001
Past symptom	499/3017 (16.5)	155/1081 (14.3)	344/1936 (17.8)	.001
Current lump detected by doctor	998/3017 (33.1)	427/1081 (39.5)	571/1936 (29.5)	<.001
Past lump detected by doctor	755/3017 (25.0)	218/1081 (20.2)	537/1936 (27.7)	<.001

Note.—Data in parentheses are percentages. Mean data are ± SDs. P values are Bonferroni adjusted by the number of features. P values less than .05 indicate statistical significance. BMI = body mass index, DM = digital mammography.

Table 3: Univariable Analysis of Relationship between Patient Demographics and Medical History to Breast Cancer Diagnosis in U.S. Data Set

Clinical Characteristic	No. of Mammography Examinations (n = 2395)	Examinations with Cancer Biopsy (n = 868)	Examinations with Noncancer Biopsy (n = 1527)	Adjusted P Value
Age (y)	2379/2395 (99.3)	63 ± 12	59 ± 11	<.001
Most recent BMI (kg/m ²)	2395/2395 (100)	31.0 ± 7.8	31.1 ± 7.2	.69
Age at first menstruation (y)	2053/2395 (85.7)	13 ± 2	13 ± 2	.61
Past benign breast diseases	86/2395 (3.6)	2/868 (0.2)	84/1527 (5.5)	<.001
Months since first DM	1383/2395 (57.7)	40.5 ± 17.9	38.3 ± 20.6	.08
Family history				
Has family member with breast cancer	220/2395 (9.2)	68/868 (7.8)	152/1527 (10.0)	.14
First-degree family member with breast cancer	7/2395 (0.3)	2/868 (0.2)	5/1527 (0.3)	.79
Medications				
Past use of fertility hormones	30/2395 (1.3)	6/868 (0.6)	24/1527 (1.6)	.14
Past use combined hormones	4/2395 (0.2)	2/868 (0.2)	2/1527 (0.1)	.62
Symptoms				
Current symptom (eg, palpable lump, nipple discharge or retraction)	38/2395 (1.6)	15/868 (1.7)	23/1527 (1.5)	.67
Past symptom	59/2395 (2.5)	17/868 (2.0)	42/1527 (2.8)	.33
Current lump detected by doctor	327/2395 (13.7)	175/868 (20.2)	152/1527 (10.0)	<.001
Past lump detected by doctor	149/2395 (6.2)	42/868 (4.8)	107/1527 (7.0)	.80

Note.—Data in parentheses are percentages. Mean data are ± SDs. P values are Bonferroni adjusted by the number of features. P values less than .05 indicate statistical significance. BMI = body mass index, DM = digital mammography.

Table 4: Performance of the AI Models for Prediction of Breast Lesion Classes in Held-Out Sets

Parameter	DCIS vs Rest	Invasive vs Rest	High Risk vs Rest	Benign vs Rest	Cancer vs Noncancer
Train and test on Israeli data					
Clinical features only	0.67 (0.60, 0.74)*	0.76 (0.71, 0.81)*	0.61 (0.49, 0.72)	0.69 (0.63, 0.75)*	0.79 (0.75, 0.84)*
Imaging features only	0.78 (0.72, 0.83)*	0.85 (0.81, 0.89)*	0.65 (0.54, 0.76)*	0.81 (0.76, 0.86)*	0.87 (0.83, 0.90)*
All features	0.76 (0.72, 0.83)*	0.85 (0.82, 0.89)*	0.65 (0.54, 0.76)*	0.82 (0.77, 0.87)*	0.88 (0.85, 0.91)*
Train on Israel, test on U.S. data					
Clinical features only	0.51 (0.42, 0.60)	0.62 (0.55, 0.69)*	0.62 (0.55, 0.69)*	0.57 (0.51, 0.63)*	0.61 (0.55, 0.67)*
Imaging features only	0.50 (0.42, 0.60)	0.82 (0.77, 0.87)*	0.62 (0.51, 0.73)*	0.65 (0.59, 0.71)*	0.61 (0.55, 0.67)*
All features	0.51 (0.42, 0.60)	0.82 (0.77, 0.89)*	0.62 (0.51, 0.73)*	0.64 (0.58, 0.70)*	0.73 (0.67, 0.79)*
Train and test on U.S. data					
Clinical features only	0.53 (0.43, 0.62)	0.64 (0.57, 0.70)*	0.57 (0.41, 0.73)	0.62 (0.56, 0.68)*	0.67 (0.60, 0.73)*
Imaging features only	0.71 (0.61, 0.81)*	0.82 (0.76, 0.88)*	0.60 (0.46, 0.73)	0.72 (0.66, 0.77)*	0.81 (0.76, 0.86)*
All features	0.74 (0.65, 0.83)*	0.83 (0.77, 0.88)*	0.60 (0.46, 0.75)	0.72 (0.66, 0.77)*	0.80 (0.74, 0.85)*
Train on U.S. data, test on Israeli data					
Clinical features only	0.47 (0.40, 0.54)	0.69 (0.63, 0.74)*	0.64 (0.52, 0.75)*	0.63 (0.56, 0.70)*	0.66 (0.60, 0.71)*
Imaging features only	0.69 (0.61, 0.76)*	0.78 (0.74, 0.83)*	0.50 (0.37, 0.62)	0.79 (0.74, 0.85)*	0.79 (0.75, 0.84)*
All features	0.69 (0.61, 0.76)*	0.77 (0.72, 0.82)*	0.47 (0.34, 0.60)	0.79 (0.74, 0.85)*	0.76 (0.71, 0.81)*

Note.—Unless otherwise indicated, data are areas under the receiver operating characteristic (AUCs); data in parentheses are 95% CIs using the DeLong method. AI = artificial intelligence, DCIS = ductal carcinoma in situ.

* AUCs that provided more predictive power than random guessing.

0.77, 0.87) for ductal carcinoma in situ, invasive carcinomas, and benign lesions, respectively.

Undoubtedly, our predictions in two classes (ie, others and high-risk lesions) had limited data, leading to poor AUCs in both

data sets. The finding of papillary lesions is relatively infrequent (incidence, 0.73%–4.00%) (19). Therefore, it is challenging to collect substantial samples in some breast lesion types, leading to controversial prognosis and clinical behavior descriptions in the

Figure 5: Graphs show comparison of the classification performance in both cohorts. Performance is reported using both imaging and clinical features. **(A)** Results of malignancy prediction in the U.S. and Israeli test sets. The marker represents the average radiologists' performance with CIs obtained with bootstrapping. **(B)** Results of prediction of invasive carcinoma versus the rest of the lesions (defined as ductal carcinoma in situ, high-risk lesions, benign lesions, and others). The models' operation point is at 90% sensitivity in the validation sets. In both **A** and **B**, the lighter lines represent the performance of the 10 trained models. The thick line is the performance of the embedded model. AUC = area under the receiver operating characteristic curve.

Figure 6: Receiver operating characteristic curve for White and African American patients in the U.S. test set. Light lines represent the performance of the 10 runs and thick lines represent the embedded model's performance. AUC = area under the receiver operating characteristic curve.

literature (20). Overall, because of the subtle differences between the defined classes and the degree of complexity of our work's goal, our AI models successfully identified the pathologic types when data were sufficiently large.

In a study where three breast radiologists were asked to assign mammograms to one of the five defined lesion classes (9),

the AI system outperformed all three breast radiologists. For the task of malignancy prediction, the AI system also outperformed all readers. When informed of patients' clinical characteristics, none of the readers changed their final decision. Similarly, in our study, we observed that adding clinical data did not improve the models' performance. However, we believe that clinical data have the potential to enable more accurate results if the data set was larger in size. In fact, improved outcomes in patients with breast cancer treated at multidisciplinary clinics have been documented (21). This suggests that a multimodality approach combining radiographic, pathologic, and clinical interpretation may provide important additional information for surgical management.

Our study had limitations. When assessing the models' generalizability, we found that they were not able to generalize across populations and screening and diagnostic mammography settings. The lower performance observed across different hospital systems can be a result of the underlying ethnic distributions of the patients from these two geographies: Whereas the Israeli population is predominantly Jewish with a sizable Arab minority, the Jewish women in the U.S. data set represented fewer than 1.1%. In addition, the large number of imaging centers in the United States, the incomplete data collected in these centers, and the variety of DM workstations could have contributed to the lack of generalizability and the overall lower performance of the U.S. models.

In conclusion, we developed a model combining a convolutional neural network with classic supervised learning algorithms trained on mammograms and linked electronic health records to classify biopsied breast lesions. Our preliminary results are encouraging and show that our models have the potential to reduce biopsy sampling errors and decrease costs associated with

false-positive findings. By grouping the breast lesions' pathologic findings according to similar clinical management guidelines, our model offers the potential to help radiologists recommend the appropriate follow-up approach on the basis of assessment of clinical, radiologic, and pathologic considerations. For example, the artificial intelligence (AI) system could be used as a safety net application where the aim is to provide an alert for cases where the radiologist's assessment of the lesion malignancy is different than the AI prediction. Although different imaging modalities and genetic information were not available in this study, we believe that, in the future, incorporating these data can help link underlying molecular differences between patients to different clinical outcomes and improve the model's diagnostic performance. Because imaging, clinical, and genomic data are collected during routine clinical practice, more resources are available for the discovery of hidden markers across modalities. Analyzing combinations of data in various forms (ie, integrating multimodal data) allows a more comprehensive understanding of breast lesion mechanisms and their impact on patient treatment. In particular, our model's ability to guide treatment planning is of immediate clinical relevance.

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